

Feminism Conflicts with Migrant Students and Workers

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Abstract

Feminism the word its not only a word it's came from the inter-feelings of feminine. The word of Migration and feminine it's the same thing, the bird also followed the migration. Is the regular seasonal Movement, often East and west , along a flyaway between breeding and wintering grounds But. Women leaving their country for studies and work, Because, they want uncertain money for some personal issues and family issues, so, they are migrant give up own emotions, desires, aim, habitual, which kind of conflicts they will meet the migration studies and works this is the major theme of the presentation.

Keywords: Discrimination, equilibrium introvert, Excretion, forerunner, interdisciplinary, Discription, conflicts, Contribution, Barriers, Waged, smear.

Introduction

To move our understanding of issues forward in-depth analysis using best impacts how to provide the fact of effects.

Classification of Conflicts

- Poverty – Economical status
- Gender Stereotype
- Hierarchies for Female
- Mental Agonies
- Discrimination of native people and migrants
- Working Priority
- Emancipation
- Tolerate another cruel activities
- Applications
- Sacrifice

It's the little bit of classification wore the female migrant students and workers which kind of phenomenon making in that migrant Place, they are hot react the feelings and emotions, just muted presents in that place. They are like a dwarf

Poverty

Studies reviewed are consistent in showing the negative impact of remittances of poverty somebody's hope only the scholarship it's the main navigation in their life

Societies of Destination

In the societies of destination gender relations and hierarchies as well as policies practices leading to gender inequalities condition the effects of migration students and workers.

Obstacles

They are confused – how to handle family issues between work issues

1. Insufficient Maternity Leave (private sector)
2. Business Plan change
3. Health issue
4. Unequal pay
5. Mental Physical harassment
6. family duties
7. Mother responsibility

Discrimination

Some Scholar Responded only the gender discrimination. The Feminist Movement has effected the discrimination. Like that woman's suffrage, hot equal pay they are not making a decision authority. Native workers or the students responding to others but, the Migrant workers and the students seats also little bit of percentage in that place migrant workers not allowed to join or form unions. Just they are always cohesion the conditional life. But, Enhanced the discrimination classifications, not reduced the traditional country, But, the great remedy in that orthodox country-just revealed their opinion-always warm-up the migrant workers.

Marital-Status also anther kind of problem, that particular women .She is the migrant women means – main controversy topic about the emotions of women.

Mental Agonies

When impoverished women decide to leave their Countries to work abroad, They often deceived or abused. The Smugglers and the organ hackers also used them, and the major cruelty – is. They are included the prostitute sector-unpaid prostitution. So, they are pushed the Gutter place. They are live only like style-corpse.

Supple Persons

Migrant women observed lots of things, But, they are not proposed to anyone , unrevealed dumps in that place. Those guys are forgotten their aim, too flexibility makes on that place, if any work, they'll done it, that is the major concept of others, because they are migrant women.

Mother Responsibility

Mother's responsibility is the main theme of women life. But, that migration women give up their child in native Land-it's the main cause of mental agonies to the migrant women. They are always thinking about the children's. It's the dead feel, It's not tolerate thinking to anyone person. They are give up the maternal feelings. Because, They are migrants –that 's Only blink in that time. They are just think this is the destiny of our life. Just lidden the emotions, feelings.

Labour Migration Vs Student Migration

It's may be same as one. Labor they are working for some commitment in personal issues-Compulsory making a job, after got money. The Students also no one find out the way of liberty from the Co-Students, Some body Studied for Scholarship amount, It's the fate – defiantly They'll Complete the studies. Both guys students and workers also making flexibility in their migrant places. Because Native place people not waged thoughts on the migrant women.

Conclusion

Migrant Women has interdisciplinary activities, and archetypal work also. But, which time they will get equilibrium in the society lots of contributions they was given the migrant places. Many kind of barriers also they had, some times the journal and the books only revealed the conflicts. That is the tiny size of reflection, but , we'll not Know about the full of form of introvert feelings of migrant woman, Some Developed Country also just smear interviews for their popularity .But, Which time the migrant woman rip the obstacles, which one is build the archive the migrant woman, Who is the fore-runner of good and equal activities making for migrant woman. But, Which time the migrant woman-they will show the door of heavens.

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